

Assessment of Malaria by 5 Part Cell Counters CBC Analysis to Improve the Sensitivity and Specificity of Diagnosis

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ABSTRACT

This study is undertaken to compare efficacy of peripheral smear (PS) and malarial antigen methods (contemporary methods of malaria diagnosis) and 5 part haematology cell counter scatterogram and flagging's in cases of malaria for effective treatment and reducing morbidity and mortality.

The study was conducted by selecting 60 cases on strong clinical suspicion, first PS and antigen test was done followed by 5 part haematological cell counter for CBC. Results were subjected to statistical analysis. CBC has a sensitivity and specificity of 96.66% and 50% respectively while peripheral smear showed 96.15% sensitivity and 16.66% specificity for detection of malaria. Antigen has sensitivity of 98.24% and specificity of 93.6%.

The study proved that various diagnostic modalities to diagnose malaria are far much better than only one diagnostic method.

KEY WORDS: 5 part cell counter scatterogram, peripheral smear, malaria antigen method.

INTRODUCTION:

The early diagnosis and treatment of malaria is necessary for the control of malaria^[1,2]. The gold standard light microscopy technique has high sensitivity, but is relatively time consuming procedure especially during epidemics and in areas of high endemicity^[3,4].

This study attempted to assess the sensitivity and specificity of a diagnostic tool which is based on the 5 part haematology cell counter ADVIA 2120 with their flagging pattern, as follows:

1. Baso Noise (B-NO,NB)
2. Comparison error WCB/WBCP(WBC-CE,WC)
3. Perox No Valley(PX-NV,VX)
4. Perox Noise(PX-NO,NX)

All scatter plots and flagging's generated due to malaria infection as per manual of Siemens

company we consider positive if either of any one "revealed".

MATERIALS & METHODS:

The study was conducted in central pathology laboratory of NKPSIMS and LMH Nagpur after obtaining clearance from Institutional Ethics Committee. Cases were selected on strong clinical suspicion of malaria if positive by traditional that is peripheral smear and antigen test. Subsequently proceeding to 5-part haematology cell counter for CBC and results were subjected to statistical analysis. Method wise distribution and comparison of malaria positive cases (proved by peripheral smear and antigen test) with 5 part haematology cell counter scatterogram and flagging's were calculated for sensitivity, specificity, negative predictive values and positive predictive values of 5 part haematology cell counter in the form of scatterogram and flagging's generated result^[5].

RESULTS:

The three diagnostic modalities gave varied result as shown in Table 1. The incidence of malaria was found to be 53.33% (32/60).

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Table 1: Results of various methods (PS, antigen and CBC).

Sr.No	Peripheral smear (PS)	CBC(flags)	Antigen	Cases	Interpretation
1	Negative	Negative	Negative	26	PS+CBC+Antigennegative
2	Negative	Positive	Negative	2	Only CBC positive
3	Negative	Negative	Positive	1	Only antigen positive
4	Negative	Positive	Positive	3	CBC+ antigen positive
5	Positive	Negative	Negative	1	Only PS positive
6	Positive	Positive	Negative	1	PS+ CBC positive
7	Positive	Negative	Positive	1	PS+ antigen positive
8	Positive	Positive	Positive	25	PS+ Antigen+ CBC positive
Total	28(46.66%)	31(51.66%)	30(50%)	60	32(53.3%)

Table 2: Distribution of species in PS, CBC and Antigen.

Species	PS(n=32)		CBC(n=32)		Antigen(n=32)	
	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
P. vivex	18(56.2%)	4(12.5%)	20 (64.06%)	1(4.68%)	20(62.5 %)	2(4.68%)
P.falciparum	7 (23.4 %)	2(4.68%)	8(25%)	1(3.12%)	9(28.12 %)	0(0%)
Mixed	1(3.12 %)	0(0%)	2 (3.12 %)	0(0%)	1(3.12 %)	0(0%)
Total	26(82.8%)	6(17.18%)	30(92.18 %)	2(7.18%)	30(93.7 %)	2(4.68%)

Table 3: Comparison of specificity, sensitivity and validity.

Test	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)
PS	96.15%	16.66%	83.33%	50%
CBC	99.66%	50%	96.67%	50%

Table 2 shows that PS was positive in 26 cases out of which 7 were plasmodium falciparum, 18 for plasmodium vivax and 1 sample were positive for mixed infection. The CBC showed 30 positive for malaria of which 8 cases were positive for P.falciparum, 20 for P.vivax and 2 for mixed infection. The antigen was positive in 30 cases with 9 being positive for P.falciparum 20 for P.vivax and 1 for mixed. Table 3 shows specificity and sensitivity of PS, CBC and antigen. We use the antigen test as a gold

standard to compare a result and calculate the sensitivity and specificity of the methods used by us. CBC had a sensitivity and specificity of 96.66% and 50% respectively while PS showed 96.15% and 16.66% for detection of malaria. Antigen has a sensitivity of 98.24% and specificity of 93.65% hence CBC had sensitivity neck to neck and specificity is differing that is PS 16.66% and CBC 50% .Hence identification is close to sensitivity whereas specificity is differing.

DISCUSSION:

In the present study three methods to detect malaria were compared, to find an easy and sensitive method for final diagnosis of Malaria. It is found that 5 part hematology cell counter method is more sensitive as antigen and is not specific as PS as well as the antigen^[5, 6, 7]. It is more specific detection modality.

CONCLUSION:

The study proved that trial of various diagnostic modalities in malaria; CBC and antigen were found superior to only one method ie peripheral smear . The new flow cytometry based system (i.e. CBC) is as sensitive as antigen and is not appear to be as specific as peripheral smear as the differentiation of both parasite locations is still not specified. However more studies with modified special stain (i.e. fluorescent) are required for generalization and justification in species specificity before establishing and recommending CBC as a new gold standard in diagnosis of malaria.

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